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Characterization of the Atmospheric Background State In Offshore Wind Farms Using GloBE Data

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Abstract. As offshore wind farms continue to increase in size, their interaction with the atmospheric boundary layer and the free atmosphere becomes important for accurate power prediction. Under specific stability regimes, particularly conventionally neutral boundary layer conditions, mesoscale flow responses such as extended blockage and gravity wave-driven pressure adjustment can significantly affect wind farm-scale power production. To capture these processes, high-fidelity large eddy simulations and lower-cost multiscale coupling models have been developed. However, applying these models to real-world datasets remains challenging because they require a consistent characterization of the atmospheric background state across the full vertical air column. This study proposes a data processing pipeline to reconstruct the atmospheric background state above offshore wind farms using measurements from the GLoBE campaign combined with atmospheric datasets of varying resolution, including global reanalysis and regional mesoscale model data. Atmospheric stability is characterized through potential temperature profile reconstruction, and the robustness of the fitting procedure is evaluated across different stability regimes. In addition, the influence of dataset resolution on the resulting distributions of key coupling parameters is assessed. The results provide guidance on the reliability of different atmospheric data sources for reconstructing physically consistent inputs for coupled wind farm-atmosphere modeling.

1. Introduction

Large wind farms can interact strongly with shallow atmospheric boundary layers (ABL) under specific conditions, as they act as farm-scale momentum sinks that modify the flow field far beyond individual turbine wakes. Capturing these interactions is crucial for predicting wind farm performance. As the atmosphere responds to the resulting momentum imbalance, processes such as pressure redistribution, entrainment, and large-scale flow adjustment play a key role in wake evolution and power generation. The way these pressure perturbations are accommodated is governed by the vertical structure of the atmosphere, which controls both the magnitude and the spatial extent of wind farm-scale (mesoscale) effects. These effects are commonly associated with global blockage and, under suitable stratification, with the excitation of interfacial or internal gravity waves. Offshore, these conditions frequently occur in conventionally neutral boundary layers (CNBL), characterized by a neutrally stratified ABL capped by a clear inversion that limits turbulent mixing and entrainment from the above stably stratified free atmosphere (FA). As a result, wind farm-induced pressure perturbations are accommodated through inversion displacement rather than through local momentum redistribution [1]. This mechanism allows pressure signals to propagate

over large distances and produce mesoscale and extended blockage effects. In particular, previous studies have shown that parameters such as ABL height, FA stratification, and inversion strength and depth are key factors governing the strength of wind farm-atmosphere coupling [1–5].

To investigate the impact of this coupling mechanism in offshore wind farms, large eddy simulation (LES) studies have been performed [5, 6], in which a limited set of predefined profiles, characterizing clear CNBL regimes, were used to conduct targeted parametric studies on key parameters driving the coupling strength: ABL height H , capping inversion strength and depth, $\Delta\theta$ and Δh , respectively, and FA lapse rate γ_{FA} . However, due to the spatial scale of the involved mesoscale phenomena, larger-than-usual numerical domains are required, leading to higher computational costs, while appropriate boundary conditions must also be applied to avoid wave reflections [5]. Linearized multi-layer coupling approaches have been developed as a low-cost alternative for linking wake dynamics, i.e., wake models, with ABL dynamics [1–3, 7, 8], through a layered representation of the atmosphere, aiming to reduce systematic errors in power prediction and thereby uncertainty in annual energy production (AEP) estimates. However, their application to real-world datasets remains challenging, since, unlike wake-only models, multiscale coupled (MSC) frameworks [9] require a consistent description of the atmospheric background state across and above the rotor layer, covering both stability and flow characteristics for a full vertical air column, in order to meaningfully evaluate the coupling strength for specific conditions.

Previous studies [5, 9] demonstrated the use of ERA5 reanalysis data to extract the distribution of key parameters driving the coupling mechanism, such as H , $\Delta\theta$, Δh , and γ_{FA} . These parameters are used to select representative potential temperature profiles for the evaluation of the coupling mechanism, either through LES simulations or within a linearized MSC framework. To do so, different fitting algorithms have been used, ranging from piecewise linear functions [9] to the smoother Rampanelli–Zardi fitting approach [5]. This raises the question of how accurate these fitting approaches are in extracting meaningful parameter distributions and whether higher resolution datasets provide measurable improvements compared to freely available alternatives. In particular, the influence of the vertical resolution of the input data on the resulting statistics of the parameter distributions, as well as the robustness of the fitting across different ABL stability regimes, remains an open question.

This study aims to address these questions by proposing a data processing pipeline for a physically consistent characterization of the atmospheric background stability above wind farms. This includes ABL stability classification and potential temperature profile reconstruction, allowing the extraction of distributions of key atmospheric parameters required for MSC modeling and LES-based studies. To demonstrate this, the methodology is applied to data from the GLoBE campaign, designed to investigate the GLoBE Blockage Effect around the Amrumbank West wind farm in the N4 wind farm cluster, and which provides a rich set of in-situ measurements. Complementary to these field observations, modeled atmospheric datasets are available, ranging from global reanalysis products such as ERA5 data to higher-resolution mesoscale simulations obtained through WRF-driven downscaling of ERA5 data, which differ substantially in spatial resolution, vertical coverage, and cost. The availability of this diverse set of data sources enables a meaningful evaluation of the previously highlighted research questions.

This paper first introduces the inputs required for characterizing the atmospheric background, as well as the available datasets (§2–§3). The methodology for ABL regime classification and potential temperature profile reconstruction is outlined in §4, including an evaluation of the fitting robustness and ABL height estimates across datasets.

2. Atmospheric background inputs for modeling

Both LES simulations and MSC models rely on realistic atmospheric input conditions for a meaningful evaluation of the wind farm-atmosphere coupling. Besides hub-height wind speed, wind direction,

and turbulence intensity, MSC models require a description of the vertical atmospheric structure in order to parameterize the background flow response. The present study focuses specifically on the characterization of atmospheric stability through potential temperature profiles, but for completeness, a complete overview of the inputs is given below.

Key required inputs include a characterization of the stability of the full atmospheric column, including both the ABL and the FA above. This is described through the potential temperature profile and derived quantities such as the ABL height H , capping-inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, FA lapse rate, γ_{FA} and reference potential temperature θ_{ref} . In addition, vertically resolved wind speed and wind direction are required to represent the background momentum distribution, while shear stress u_\star and eddy viscosity ν_t quantify vertical momentum transport and mixing efficiency. Finally, a small set of environmental parameters, such as air density ρ , the Coriolis parameter f_c , site latitude ϕ , and characteristic layer heights (ground, wind farm, and ABL height), should be specified. The schematic shown in figure 1 provides an overview of the required inputs within the MSC framework, with the parameters of particular interest for this study highlighted in bold.

Figure 1. Overview of the inputs required by the MSC model, including bulk-averaged parameters describing stratification and momentum exchange, as well as additional environmental parameters. The parameters of interest for this study are highlighted in bold.

While many numerical studies prescribe idealized atmospheric states through controlled parameter combinations, the objective here is to reconstruct atmospheric inputs that best represent the observed atmospheric conditions during the measurement campaign. The following sections, therefore, describe which data sources are useful in this study and how they are combined to derive a physically consistent description of the atmospheric state that can be used as input for the modeling framework.

3. Data sources and measurement infrastructure

For the present study, data from in-situ measurements during the GLOBE campaign [4] is used. The campaign took place in the N4 wind farm cluster in the German Bight and collected field observations from different measurement systems located in and around the following three wind farms: Amrumbank West (ABW), Nordsee Ost (NSO) and Meerwind Süd/Ost (MSO). This includes meteorological data from the mast, providing wind speed, wind direction, and atmospheric stability information, with derived quantities such as the Monin-Obukhov (MO) length L . Complementary to this, scanning and profiling LiDARS were deployed to extract horizontal and vertical information on the wind field and atmospheric structure, including ABL heights. The in-situ measurements are

complemented by mesoscale WRF simulations, provided by Fraunhofer IWES within the X-Wakes project, and freely available ECMWF ReAnalysis data (ERA5), which are both extracted at latitude 54.5° and longitude 7.75° . Additionally, Vortex data, produced through WRF-based downscaling of ERA5 data and made available by Ørsted, offer an additional, high-resolution representation of the large-scale atmospheric conditions. In what follows, IWES-WRF, ERA5, and Vortex-WRF will be used to refer to the WRF simulations, the ECMWF ReAnalysis data, and the combined downscaled dataset, respectively. Figure 2 shows the layout of the N4 cluster and the surrounding measurement infrastructure. Note that the profiling LiDAR, installed on the buoy, changed location twice during the measurement campaign and is represented by the blue pentagon in the figure. Table 1 shows the time availability of the different data sources and their overlapping period.

Figure 2. Layout of the N4 cluster, highlighting the Amrumbank West wind farm and the surrounding measurement infrastructure.

Type of Data	Start Date	End Date
Mast data	2021-08-09	2023-02-13
Profiling LiDAR	2021-08-15	2022-04-26
WRF data	2019-01-01	2022-12-31
Vortex data	2021-01-01	2022-12-31
Common period	2021-08-15	2022-04-26

Table 1. Data availability across different data sources

4. ABL-regime classification and profile extraction

Different from controlled simulation environments, real ABLs undergo diurnal cycles in which different regimes are formed. This process is driven by surface forcing, as cooling and warming of the Earth’s surface cause the neutrally stratified boundary layer (NBL) to evolve into either a stable (SBL) or convective (CBL) boundary layer, including transitional states (see the upper right panel of the schematic in figure 1). In maritime conditions, as considered in this study, the high heat capacity of water dampens this diurnal evolution, often leading to a predominance of near-neutral and weakly unstable conditions rather than strongly stable cases [1, 10].

This section characterizes atmospheric stability in the ABL and FA to identify CNBL conditions. ABL regimes are first classified using in-situ metrics and a bulk flow-based approach. Potential temperature profiles are then fitted to datasets of different vertical resolutions, and their robustness towards different ABL regimes is evaluated. A comparative analysis of ABL height estimates with other ABL height sources is performed.

4.1. Limitations of point-based stability metrics

A first approach to identify CNBL conditions is to select periods in which the ABL exhibits nearly height-independent potential temperature, indicative of near-neutral stratification based on point-based stability metrics. In this study, met-mast observations are used to derive the MO length, L , evaluated at multiple heights, as well as the variables required to compute the gradient Richardson number, Ri . Mesoscale IWES-WRF output also supplies estimates of L at the height of the first model grid cell. These metrics are widely used in wind energy applications and form a

natural starting point for stability classification.

However, both L and Ri are rooted in Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (MOST) and are therefore formally valid only within the surface layer, typically assumed to be the lowest $\sim 10\%$ of the ABL. This limitation becomes particularly problematic for wind farm applications, where turbine hub heights and rotor areas extend well above the surface layer, especially under shallow ABL conditions. As seen from Equations (1) and (2), representing the formulation of L and Ri , both metrics are based on locally evaluated quantities: L depends on the turbulent heat flux $\overline{w'\theta'}$, while Ri relies on local vertical gradients of virtual potential temperature and wind speed, $d\theta/dz$ and du/dz , respectively. As a result, these metrics are sensitive to measurement height, vertical resolution, and small-scale variability, leading to potentially large inconsistencies across evaluation heights.

$$L = -\frac{u_*^3 \theta}{\kappa g \overline{w'\theta'}} \quad (1) \quad , \quad Ri = \frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta}{dz} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{du}{dz}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

This is illustrated in figure 3, which compares stability classifications based on the MO length following Bardal et al. [11]. Classifications derived from met-mast measurements at 32 m and 92 m are compared with those from IWES-WRF output at the height of the first model grid cell. Pronounced differences occur across heights and data sources, with conditions classified as neutral by one source or height not necessarily classified as such by another. Moreover, it is often unclear whether the evaluation height lies within the surface layer. These inconsistencies show that point-based stability metrics do not robustly characterize ABL stability at turbine-relevant heights, motivating a bulk-flow-based approach spanning the full rotor layer and the air above.

(a) Met mast stability at 32 m vs IWES-WRF

(b) Met mast stability at 92 m vs IWES-WRF

Figure 3. Confusion matrices of stability classifications based on met mast and IWES-WRF data

4.2. Bulk-flow stability classification using potential temperature differences

The bulk-flow stability classification approach used in this study is the potential temperature difference (PTD) method developed by Liu and Liang [10]. This method evaluates the difference in potential temperature between two levels encompassing the rotor layer and the air aloft and classifies the flow into CBL, NBL, and SBL regimes based on the sign and magnitude of this difference, given by the parameter σ . In this study, the PTD is evaluated between lower and upper limits of 50 m and 250 m, respectively, consistent with the turbine dimensions at the wind farm site. Because

met-mast measurements do not cover this height range, additional data sources are required to characterize the thermal structure across the rotor layer and the air immediately above. Radiosonde soundings could, in principle, provide this information, but such observations are rarely available at offshore wind farm sites. Instead, mesoscale model outputs such as WRF (e.g., Vortex-WRF and IWES-WRF) can be used, providing high-resolution vertical profiles of temperature and pressure up to 500 m, from which potential temperature can be derived over the relevant height range. When high-resolution mesoscale model data are unavailable, ERA5 reanalysis data offer an alternative for computing potential temperature and related stability metrics. However, care must be taken, as the lower part of the potential temperature profile may not be fully resolved.

$$\text{PTD} = \theta_{upper} - \theta_{lower} = \begin{cases} < -\sigma, & \text{CBL (unstable)} \\ > +\sigma, & \text{SBL (stable)} \\ \in [-\sigma, +\sigma], & \text{NBL (neutral)} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In this study, a PTD threshold σ of 0.2 K is used for maritime conditions to isolate the different regimes. Note that this threshold is typically lower than for terrestrial conditions because of the higher heat capacity of water. The PTD-based stability classification using the Vortex-WRF data results in relative occurrences of 3%, 61%, and 36% for CBL, NBL, and SBL, respectively, reflecting weaker offshore thermal stratification in maritime conditions compared to on land [10]. For comparison, the same analysis is performed using ERA5 data, showing an approximately 20% shift from NBL to SBL cases, reflecting the limited vertical resolution of ERA5 and the need for high resolution data for accurate ABL regime classification.

Figure 4a shows a stacked histogram of the PTD distribution for all available timestamps, color-coded by the metmast-based stability classification, using MO-length L , and with dashed lines representing the threshold values of ± 0.2 K for regime classification. The figure highlights cases in which the PTD method indicates an NBL regime while near-surface metrics classify the flow as stable or unstable. These differences underscore the importance of a bulk-flow stability assessment for correctly identifying ABL regimes relevant to wind farm applications. Note that for ideal CNBL conditions, a PTD of 0 K is required, representing a perfectly mixed layer and thus a neutrally stratified ABL. However, truly neutral conditions are rare in the atmosphere. Therefore, a finite threshold is adopted in order to account for measurement uncertainty and weak residual stratification. Additionally, figure 4b provides insight into the distribution of ABL heights for the different ABL stability regimes. It can be clearly observed that SBL regimes suppress the growth of the ABL, resulting in low ABL height values, while the opposite is true for the more turbulent CBL cases.

4.3. Potential Temperature Profile Fitting

The next step in identifying CNBL regimes is characterizing the stability of the vertical air column between the ABL and the FA, as the presence of a clear capping inversion needs to be detected. This is achieved by fitting an analytical potential temperature profile to the available data. Following previous studies [5, 6, 9, 12], the smooth profile of Rampanelli and Zardi [13] is used, but with the modification proposed by S. Stipa [9] to accommodate weakly positive or negative temperature gradients within the ABL associated with the relaxed threshold $\sigma = 0.2$ K. The analytical expression is given by

$$\theta(z) = \theta_{\text{ref}} + a f(\xi) + b g(\xi) + d I(\xi) + \gamma_{\text{ABL}} H \quad \text{with} \quad \xi = \frac{z - H}{c \Delta h}, \quad (4)$$

and is designed to optimally capture the CNBL profile-related parameters. In this expression, ξ is the non-dimensional vertical coordinate defined as a function of geopotential height z , ABL height H , and inversion depth Δh , where the parameter c controls the smoothness of the transition between

Figure 4. (a) Histogram of the PTD, stacked by the surface stability class determined from the MO length L at 92 m at the met mast. The red dashed lines indicate the thresholds separating the ABL regimes CBL, NBL, and SBL. (b) Distribution of the ABL height for the different ABL regimes and for the full dataset.

the different layers. The parameters θ_{ref} and γ_{ABL} represent the reference potential temperature and the lapse rate in the ABL. The functions $f(\xi)$, $g(\xi)$, and $I(\xi)$ are constructed to describe the rapid transition across the inversion layer and the asymptotic variation of potential temperature in the FA and the ABL. The influence of mixing processes at the top of the ABL and warming within the mixed layer on the resulting θ profile is reflected in the scaling of the coefficients a and b in front of the functions $f(\xi)$ and $g(\xi)$. In particular, parameter a , expressed as $a = c\gamma_{FA}\Delta h$, is of interest for this study as it quantifies the entrainment of FA air, which strengthens the capping inversion and thereby increases the likelihood of CNBL conditions [13]. Note that in a previous study [12], an additional basis function was introduced to account for non-constant surface layer temperature or SBL conditions. This extension is not adopted here, although alternative approaches have been explored, which are not further discussed here.

The fitting algorithm is applied to two different datasets, ERA5 and the higher-resolution Vortex-WRF data, spanning the years 2021 and 2022. This period is selected instead of the full overlapping availability of the different data sources to avoid seasonal effects influencing the results and to enable better comparison with previous research [9]. Figure 7a visualizes several randomly picked potential temperature profiles using both datasets at corresponding timestamps. Due to its lower vertical resolution, the ERA5 data does not always resolve near-surface features well and is therefore extrapolated to the ground using the gradient at the lowest available level. Additionally, to assess the robustness of the fitting algorithm, it is applied on all ABL stability regimes: CBL, NBL and SBL. The resulting profiles are fitted using weighted nonlinear least squares with physically motivated upper and lower bounds of the parameters involved. Especially, ABL information is of high importance at this stage to guide the model towards correct fitting. This is discussed in more detail in the following subsection. The fit quality using both datasets is evaluated using the coefficient of determination R^2 , comparing the raw data and the fitted profile.

Figure 5 shows the relationship between the PTD and the goodness-of-fit metric R^2 for ERA5 (a) and Vortex-WRF (b) data. The distributions of both variables are shown along the axes, while the binned mean of R^2 highlights the overall trend. The inset frames below the legend additionally visualize the point density in the same R^2 -PTD space, with darker colors indicating zones of higher point density. Overall, using the Vortex-WRF data results in a higher fit performance compared to the ERA5 data. For both datasets, however, R^2 decreases with increasing PTD, corresponding to more stable bulk flow conditions, with a stronger effect visible when using the ERA5 data. This downward trend is expected, as the analytical fitting expression is not designed for such conditions.

Both plots are color-coded by the fitted entrainment parameter a , which reflects the increasing likelihood of CNBL conditions. It can be observed that cases with the highest a -value show the best fit performance, i.e., ± 0.8 , in the red zones, and are situated within the NBL regime. Those cases are likely CNBL conditions for which a clear inversion layer is present, as the Rampanelli–Zardi formulation is specifically designed to represent such profiles. Note that the fitting performance for these conditions using the ERA5 data is almost equally good to the Vortex-WRF data-driven fitting. The density inset frames highlight that this red zone of high entrainment values coincides with the highest concentration of samples, i.e., the black zone, supporting the frequent occurrence of CNBL regimes in offshore atmospheric conditions [1]. For the Vortex-WRF data-based fitting, this region of high point concentration appears less diluted than for the ERA5-based fitting, supporting the improved fitting performance obtained when using higher resolution data.

Figure 5. Relationship between PTD and the coefficient of determination R^2 for the Rampanelli–Zardi potential temperature profile fitting applied to the raw input profiles. The goodness-of-fit metric is shown for (a) ERA5 and (b) Vortex-WRF data, with points color-coded by the fitted entrainment parameter a . The blue line represents the binned mean of R^2 , and the small inset frame visualizes the point density in the same space.

Next, the distributions of the extracted parameters driving the coupling mechanism of both results are compared. This includes H , γ_{FA} , $\Delta\theta$, Δh and θ_{ref} . To investigate this, the KDEs of the above-mentioned fitted parameters are shown in figure 6 for both the ERA5 (red) and the Vortex-WRF data (blue), together with the correlation coefficient r . The distributions obtained using the ERA5 data agree with those from literature [5, 9]. For H , γ_{FA} , $\Delta\theta$ and θ_{ref} , there is a moderate to strong correlation between the values obtained from both fittings. Vortex-WRF data-based fitting shows lower values of ABL height H , which is favorable since the coupling strength is expected to increase under shallow ABL conditions [5]. The $\Delta\theta$ peak shifts by approximately 1 K to higher values, while the inversion width Δh , which shows a lower correlation, tends to have smaller values around 200 m. Consequently, there is a higher probability near 100 m, which supports the commonly used choice of a 100 m inversion width as a representative inversion depth in previous studies [5, 9], as it is more favorable for the excitation of inversion waves. Figure 7b shows fitted profiles for 20 randomly picked timestamps, color-coded based on a threshold value for the entrainment parameter a , with high a values isolating typical CNBL regimes. For both classes, one exemplary profile is highlighted.

Figure 6. KDE distributions of the fitted parameters: ABL height H , FA lapse rate γ_{FA} , capping inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, inversion depth Δh , and reference potential temperature θ_{ref} . The ERA5 (red) and Vortex-WRF (blue) datasets are shown together with their correlation coefficient r .

Figure 7. Examples of potential temperature profiles used for the analysis with both Vortex-WRF (blue) data and ERA5 data (red) extrapolated to the ground. (b) Randomly selected Rampanelli–Zardi fitted profiles, highlighting two exemplary cases: a CNBL and an NBL without inversion.

4.4. ABL-estimates

To ensure robust convergence of the fitting algorithm, appropriate initial parameter estimates are required. In particular, the ABL height plays a crucial role in guiding the fitting procedure. Therefore, an initial estimate of the ABL height was obtained by taking the mean value of the available data sources. For the ERA5 data-based fitting, this is done using the ABL height provided by ERA5 and the LiDAR measurement, while for the Vortex-WRF data-based fitting, ABL height estimates from both the IWES-WRF and Vortex-WRF datasets were additionally included. In addition, two commonly used diagnostic approaches were applied to provide independent estimates of the ABL height: the bulk Richardson number Ri_b method and the potential temperature threshold method, using a threshold of 2 K. Detailed descriptions of these methods can be found in the relevant literature [14]. Figure 8a shows the KDEs of the ABL heights obtained from the different sources used as input for the Vortex-WRF data-based fitting, with the profile-fitted ABL heights included for comparison with the label 'RZ' for Rampanelli-Zardi. Only timestamps within the common time period are used in the analysis. It can be observed that most KDEs show a similar distribution, with the exception of the LiDAR measurements. These show a pronounced and narrow peak around 500 m and do not detect ABL heights above 1000 m.

Figure 8b shows the difference in ABL estimation between the fitting and the different methods as a function of the PTD. The curves present smoothed trends, and dashed lines represent the threshold $\pm \sigma$ for ABL regime classification. It can clearly be observed that LiDAR measurements

only match the other sources for PTD values between 0 and 1 K, with lower and higher detected ABL heights for unstable and stable atmospheres, respectively. This highlights the need for careful evaluation when deriving ABL heights from LiDAR measurements.

Finally, figure 8c presents a heatmap illustrating the correlation between the ABL-heights obtained from the Vortex-WRF data-based fitting results, labeled as 'RZ', and those estimated by the other methods. A notably good agreement is observed between the Vortex-WRF data-based estimates and the numerical methods considered. It should be noted, however, that these numerical estimates are calculated using the high-resolution Vortex-WRF data in this case, which likely contributes to their improved agreement. Nevertheless, the results highlight the potential of these approaches as reliable methods in ABL height estimation. In contrast, ERA5 and IWES-WRF show slightly weaker correlations with the fitted ABL heights. The blue zones indicate the relatively weak correlation associated with the LiDAR measurements.

Figure 8. Comparison of ABL height estimates from different sources with the RZ-fitted ABL height: (a) KDE distribution, (b) difference versus PTD, and (c) correlation matrix for the different ABL height sources.

5. Conclusion

This study presents a data processing pipeline to reconstruct the atmospheric background stability above offshore wind farms using measurements from the GLoBE campaign. The first step focused on determining the stability of the lower ABL. Initially, in-situ stability metrics were considered. However, these surface-based stability measures vary strongly with measurement height and therefore do not necessarily represent the stability of the entire ABL. This limitation motivates the use of a bulk flow-based stability approach. In this study, the PTD method was adopted, and the resulting ABL regime classification is consistent with the expected dominance of near-neutral and weakly stable regimes in offshore atmospheric conditions, given the low thermal response of the ocean surface. Notable differences were found in the relative occurrence of ABL regimes when using the lower-resolution ERA5 data, emphasizing the need for higher-resolution datasets for accurate stability classification.

To extract the distributions of the key parameters driving the wind farm-atmosphere coupling, the Rampanelli-Zardi profile fitting approach was applied. The fitting was performed using datasets with different vertical resolutions, showing that higher-resolution datasets improve the fitting quality across all regimes. For cases with a high fitted entrainment parameter a , suggesting a CNBL with a clear capping inversion, the fitting performance using ERA5 data is nearly comparable to that obtained with the higher resolution Vortex-WRF data. The resulting parameter distributions show generally good agreement with the literature, with a tendency toward higher inversion strength $\Delta\theta$ and lower inversion depth Δh and height H in the higher-resolution dataset, which is favorable for

increased coupling strength.

Additionally, a comparative analysis was performed between ABL height estimates from different sources, including the fitted profiles, model data, in-situ LiDAR measurements, and numerical diagnostic approaches. The results show generally good agreement between the numerical methods and the fit- and model-based estimates. In contrast, LiDAR-derived ABL heights only show consistent agreement with the other methods for near-neutral and weakly stable conditions, indicating that careful interpretation of these measurements is required when using them for ABL height estimation in assessment of wind farm-atmosphere coupling studies.

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